

INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS FOR ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AND ASSESSMENT

Raximova Muxlisa Nozim kizi

Tashkent State Pedagogical University

English Language and Literature 3rd year student

Xatira Gaybullayeva Muratdzhanovna

Tashkent State Pedagogical University

Faculty of Philology Department of English Language Theory and Methodology

Associate Professor, PHD

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Abstract. This article discusses international standards for English language teaching and assessment, their content, didactic requirements, and the advantages of integrating them into the educational process. In the modern education system, international standards such as CEFR, TOEFL, and IELTS allow students to assess their linguistic competencies based on specific criteria. The study analyzes the scientific basis of CEFR language proficiency levels, communicative approach, assessment criteria, language skills teaching methods, and testing systems. It also presents proposals for implementing international assessment standards in national educational programs, improving teacher training, and modernizing the teaching process. The results show that the adaptation of English language teaching to global requirements is an important factor in improving the quality of education, developing students' communicative competence, and shaping them as competitive personnel in the international arena.

Keywords: CEFR, assessment criteria, language competencies, international standards, English language education, communicative approach, testing system.

In the current era of globalization, English is strengthening its position as the language of international communication, science, technology and diplomacy. Therefore, the implementation of international standards for effective teaching and assessment of English in the educational process is one of the important factors in improving the quality of education. The experience of different countries shows that a standardized approach ensures consistency, effectiveness and objective assessment in the teaching process.

The main purpose of international standards is to clearly indicate to the student the level of knowledge of the language, what skills he has and how much he can use English in real-life situations.[1]

The following article will cover the content, assessment criteria, teaching methods and the scientific and practical significance of their application in Uzbekistan.

International standards for teaching English

CEFR - Common European Framework of Reference for Languages. CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) is the most widely used universal standard for determining language proficiency today. It includes the following 6 levels:

A1 (Beginner) - elementary level

A2 (Elementary) - above elementary

B1 (Intermediate) - intermediate level

B2 (Upper-Intermediate) - upper intermediate level

C1 (Advanced) - advanced level

C2 (Proficient) - excellent level[2]

The advantage of CEFR is that it assesses not only grammatical knowledge, but also skills such as communicative competence, cultural competence, strategic competence.

IELTS system. IELTS assesses 4 main English language skills:

Listening

Reading

Writing

Speaking[3]

The IELTS band system (0–9) clearly indicates the student's level of language proficiency in a global standard.

TOEFL system. TOEFL is the main assessment system for US universities and is conducted online (iBT). It is assessed on a 120-point scale.

The advantage of TOEFL is that it is based on academic English.

The use of international standards in teaching

Communicative approach. The main requirement of CEFR and other systems is that the student must be able to use the language in real life. Therefore, in the lessons:

communication exercises,

authentic materials,

role-playing games,

discussions,

project work

are widely used.[4]

Differentiated teaching. Since specific results are set for each level, the teacher can give assignments that are appropriate for the individual capabilities of students.

The teacher no longer acts as a source of information, but as a facilitator, trainer, motivator.

International assessment systems

Formative assessment. This assessment monitors the student's development throughout the process. Examples:

mini-tests

interviews

oral reports

small written assignments

Summative assessment. At the end of the course, the following are used to clearly determine the student's qualifications:

midterm exam

final exam

certification tests

International requirements for test tasks They ensure the following:

objectivity

reliability

fairness

multi-stage

closeness to real situations

A national version of the CEFR was adopted in Uzbekistan in 2013. Today:

schools,

colleges,

higher education institutions,

language centers

are adapting their educational process to the CEFR.

Existing problems

Different levels of teacher qualifications

Lack of materials

Subjectivity in assessment

Insufficient technical equipment[5]

Due to the establishment of specific results for each level, teaching becomes consistent.

Increases student motivation

The student clearly knows his level and sees his development.

Ensures a balance of student skills

Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing skills develop harmoniously with each other.

Internationally recognized

CEFR-based certificates are accepted in many countries.

Create methodological convenience for the teacher Each topic, task, and assessment criterion is predetermined.

In conclusion, basing English language education on international standards is the most important condition for adapting to global educational requirements. Systems such as CEFR, IELTS, TOEFL increase the effectiveness of education by developing students' communicative competence, ensuring the objectivity of external assessment, and providing clear instructions to teachers. Deep integration of these standards in the Uzbek education system will serve to cultivate competitive, qualified young people in all aspects.

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